

The sad fate of Alfred Russel Wallace's brother Edward and the rediscovery of his burial place in Brazil

By George Beccaloni & Ildeu de Castro Moreira, March 2026

Silhouette of Herbert Edward Wallace, aged 20, made shortly before he sailed for Brazil.

From [My Life](#). This is one of only two surviving images of Edward.

[The other is a sketch](#) made when he was eight years old.

When Alfred Russel Wallace left England in 1848 with his friend [Henry Walter Bates](#) to collect natural history specimens in the Amazon, the venture was as much an economic gamble as a scientific expedition. Alfred intended to finance his travels by collecting specimens of insects, birds and other animals that could be sold to museums and private collectors in Britain. Within a year, another member of the Wallace family would join him in Brazil: his youngest brother Herbert Edward Wallace ("Edward") (1829–1851). The brief career of this little-known participant in the Amazon expedition ended tragically in 1851, when he died in Pará (Belém) during a yellow-fever epidemic.

Research done by the authors in 2017, but unpublished until now, suggests that Edward's burial place can be identified with some confidence: the Protestant cemetery that once served

the British community in Belém, today forming the grounds of the Catedral Anglicana de Santa Maria (the Belém Anglican Church).

Colourised reconstruction by ChatGPT of what Edward might have looked like, based on the above silhouette and his age.

Edward's Amazon venture

Like many young men of modest means in mid-Victorian Britain, Edward faced uncertain employment prospects. By 1849 Alfred was already established in the Amazon collecting natural-history specimens for sale in Britain, and Edward decided to join him. He sailed for Brazil on 7 June 1849 and reached Belém in early July. As Alfred later recalled in [My Life](#), Edward accompanied him essentially as an apprentice, learning the practical skills of collecting insects and preparing specimens for shipment to Alfred's London agent, Samuel Stevens, with the aim that he might eventually become an independent collector himself.

In August 1849 Alfred and Edward began travelling up the Amazon, stopping at towns along the river to collect. They reached Barra do Rio Negro (now Manaus) on 31 December. Soon afterwards Alfred set off to explore the Rio Negro, leaving Edward to collect near the town. Alfred returned in May 1850, departing in August on a longer expedition up the Rio Negro. It was probably during the period when the brothers were together in Manaus that Alfred realised that Edward was unlikely to succeed as a professional collector. He wrote in [My Life](#):

"After a year's experience it was now clear that my brother was not fitted to become a good natural-history collector, as he took little interest in birds or insects, and without enthusiasm in the pursuit he would not have been likely to succeed. We therefore arranged that he should stay at or near Barra for a few months of the dry season, make what collections he could, then return to Para on his way home. I left him what money I could spare, and as he was now well acquainted with the country, and could, if absolutely necessary, get an advance from our agents at Para, I had little doubt that he would get home without difficulty. But I never saw him again."

In May 1851 Edward had reached the port city of Belém. There he secured passage on a ship bound for Liverpool that was due to depart on 6 June, and he remained in the city awaiting the vessel's sailing. It was during this period that tragedy struck. The Amazonian ports were periodically devastated by epidemics of yellow fever, then commonly known as "black vomit" because of one of the disease's most horrifying symptoms. Edward unfortunately contracted it.

The events surrounding Edward's death are described in a letter written on 13 June 1851 by Henry Walter Bates to Alfred's mother. In it ([WCP1658](#)), Bates reported the sad news that Edward had "breathed his last ... a victim of the fatal black vomit." Despite medical attention, the disease had progressed rapidly. A second letter from Bates later that year ([WCP1659](#)) gives a moving account of Edward's final hours. According to a friend present at his bedside¹, he realised only shortly before the end that his condition was fatal, remarking simply that it was "very sad to die so young."² He passed away on the morning of 8 June 1851, aged only twenty-two.³

Alfred did not learn of his brother's death until a year later, as he had been travelling in the remote Rio Negro region.

Where was Edward buried?

The letters reporting Edward's death do not record the place of burial. This absence has left historians uncertain about where he was laid to rest.

However, historical context strongly narrows the possibilities. In nineteenth-century Brazil, non-Catholics were generally excluded from burial in Catholic cemeteries. Foreign Protestant communities therefore established their own burial grounds. British residents in several Brazilian ports created such "English cemeteries" specifically for Protestant burials. Belém possessed such a burial ground, known locally as the *Cemitério Protestante*. It served the British and foreign Protestant community of the city during the nineteenth century.

In 1912, more than sixty years after Edward's death, an Anglican chapel was constructed within this cemetery. The church was founded by the Anglican missionary and naturalist [Arthur Miles Moss](#) (1873-1948), who arrived in Belém in 1911 to organise Anglican ministry across the Amazon region. Moss was Chaplain from 1912 to 1930. After his retirement, he returned to the region and voluntarily continued his ministry as Honorary Chaplain until 1945. In that same year, he returned to England, residing in the Lake District, the area he had spent his childhood ([Barros, 2006](#)).

Catedral Anglicana de Santa Maria in 2006. Osmar Arouck: Wikimedia Commons

A forgotten memorial rediscovered

The connection between Alfred Wallace, Bates and this church emerged unexpectedly from a [diary entry written in 1927](#) by the Oxford anthropologist Henry Balfour (1863-1939). During a visit to Belém he recorded that he had visited the “little English church, where is a gunmetal tablet to Bates, Wallace etc.” This tantalising remark prompted a search for the memorial Balfour mentioned.

The plaque still exists. Installed inside the Anglican church, probably in 1926 (see [WCP6149](#)), it commemorates several nineteenth-century naturalists who worked in the Amazon, including Bates, Alfred Wallace and others associated with the region’s early exploration. Crucially, the inscription also mentions Edward Wallace and states that he died of yellow fever in Belém and is buried in the cemetery surrounding the church.⁴ This inscription provides the strongest evidence yet that Edward’s remains lie in the old Protestant cemetery that now forms the grounds of the church.

The plaque inside the church. © Joseane Paula

TO THE HONOUR AND GLORY OF GOD
AND IN THE CAUSE OF TRUTH
THIS TABLET IS ERECTED
ECCLESIASTICUS XLIV

1. Let us now praise famous men, and our fathers that begat us
7. All these were honoured in their generations and were the glory of their time
14. Their bodies are buried in Peace, but their name liveth forever

This tablet is erected to the memory of that intrepid group of
amazon river explorers whose character and spirit exemplify
the noble traditions and lofty ideals of our race and whose
lives and achievements are an inspiration to all who follow.

RICHARD SPRUCE
Born September 10, 1817 – Died December 28, 1893

ALFRED RUSSEL WALLACE
Born January 8, 1823 – Died November 7, 1913

HENRY WALTER BATES
Born February 8, 1825 – Died February 16, 1892

WILLIAM CHANDLESS
Born November 7, 1829 – Died June 5, 1896

HERBERT EDWARD WALLACE
Born May 31, 1829 – Died June 8, 1851
A victim of yellow fever in Pará and is buried in this cemetery

“Ye shall know the truth
And the truth shall make you free”
St. John. VIII - 32

Wording on the plaque

Why Edward was buried there

Given the circumstances of his death, burial in the Protestant cemetery is exactly what one would expect. Edward was a British Protestant who died in Belém during an epidemic. The British community maintained its own burial ground precisely for such cases. The Anglican chapel built there in 1912 simply occupied ground that had already served as the burial place of foreigners for decades.

Although Edward's grave marker has not been located (one may not have existed, or if it did, it was subsequently destroyed), the memorial plaque confirms that he was interred within this cemetery.

Edward's brief life illustrates the risks faced by the naturalists who ventured to the tropics in the nineteenth century. Disease claimed many victims among explorers, traders and missionaries in the Amazon basin. For Alfred, Edward's death was one of several personal tragedies during his Amazon expedition. Within a year Alfred himself would lose all his collections from the last two most interesting years of his expedition and nearly his life as well, when his return ship caught fire in the Atlantic.

Edward's last poem

Edward was passionate about poetry, and a number of the poems he wrote in Brazil survive, including one he wrote not long before his death. In [My Life](#), Alfred writes the following: "The following poem is probably the last written by my brother. There is no draft or note of it in his rough note-book, and it is written out carefully on a sheet of thin letter-paper which he probably obtained in Para. It was therefore almost certainly written during the two weeks before his fatal illness."

"OUR BETTER MOMENTS.

Uncalled they come across the mind,
We know not why or how,
And with instinctive reverence
Ignoble feelings bow:
A power strange, yet holy too,
Breathes through our every sense;
Each atom of our being feels
Its subtle influence.
High visions, noble thinkings, flash
Like meteors through the brain,
If Paradise was lost to us,
'Tis surely come again!

Better moments! Better moments! Ye are sunny angels' wings, Sent to shed a holier radiance o'er all dim and worldly things.

Perchance we love to watch awhile,
In simple child-like mood,
The waving of the summer grass,
The ebbing of the flood,

Or lie upon a mossy bank
In some secluded shade,
When sudden, from before our gaze,
The grass—the waters fade;
And giving up our being's rein
To unknown guiding hands,
We float in passive confidence
To voiceless spirit lands.

Better moments! Better moments! Ye are sunny angels' wings, Sent to shed a holier radiance
o'er all dim and worldly things.

Or sitting in a leafy wood,
Some still and breathless hour,
The joyous twitter of a bird
Has strange unconscious power;
The power to send through ev'ry nerve
A thrill of soft delight;
A better moment, like the dawn,
Steals in with ambient light;
The soul expands, and lovingly
Takes in its pure embrace,
All life! all nature! high or mean,
Of colour, tongue, or race.

Better moments! Better moments! Ye are sunny angels' wings, Sent to shed a holier radiance
o'er all dim and worldly things.

A thousand various scenes and tones
Awake the better thought,
By which our duller years of life
Become inspired and taught.
In olden times there rudely came
Handwriting on the wall,
And prostrate souls fell horror-struck
At that wild spirit-call;
But now God's momentary gleam
Is sent into the soul
To guide uncertain wavering feet
To Life's high solemn goal.

Better moments! Better moments! Ye are sunny angels' wings, Sent to shed a holier radiance
o'er all dim and worldly things."

Acknowledgements

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Endnotes

1. This was Daniel Miller (?-1851), consignee of the ship that brought Alfred Wallace and Bates in 1848, a merchant and British vice-consul who greatly helped the two naturalists in Belém. According to Bates, Miller helped take care of Herbert in his final days, but also died a few days later from yellow fever.
2. Bates relates that "Towards his end he folded his hands as if in prayer & died in strong convulsions."
3. Interestingly, in his letter, Bates mentions that Edward's "collections were sent home entire by the next vessel addressed to Mr Stevens, they contained a great variety of miscellaneous curiosities."
4. Daniel Miller was buried there too.

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